

IMPACTS OF INVESTMENTS FOR REGIONAL AND LOCAL DEVELOPMENT; THE CASE OF GWADAR

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Abstract. Gwadar is increasingly important in supporting Pakistan's ailing economy. It is quite astounding how quickly Gwadar, a little fishing hamlet in Pakistan, is developing into a major international deep-water port. Given the significance of the area, the Pakistani government has designated Gwadar as a duty-free port and free economic zone. The foreign direct investment (FDI) from China will have great multiple impacts on the regional infrastructure changes and on the government's economy directly.

Keywords. investment effects, capitalizing, multiplier effects, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

Introduction

The strength and stability of a nation are fundamentally dependent on its economy, which is a key component of national power. The Gwadar port will entice investors, generate employment opportunities, open up new avenues for economic growth in the coastal area, and boost the national economy significantly. In addition, the port is a very important national demand given the increase in cargo volume at current ports. More crucially, the Gwadar project has resulted in a number of positive side projects, including the Saindak project, industrial estates in the area, and the Makran coastal highway. In order to make this project comprehensive and competitive, coordinated efforts must be made to create an environment that is suitable to the industrialization of this area based on plans, programmers, and scientific approach and efficient directions.

Image 1.1 Gwadar Sea Port**Transportation links**

The Gwadar project depends on the Makran Coastal Highway, which runs 675 miles between Gwadar and Karachi. The road construction is almost finished which will have great impact on; both domestic and foreign investors will have access to the region's commercial potential. Additionally, it has connected Iran and Karachi, creating a new and more direct economic route between the two nations.

Figure 1.1 Road Map of Gwadar

Contribution of Foreign Investment

The Pakistan Economic Corridors Program (PECP), which the Asian Development Bank (ADB) and the Government of the United Kingdom Department for International Development (DFID) agreed to in February 2015, will assist the government's efforts to improve regional trade and connectivity, spur economic growth, and create jobs. The initiative consists of three components: (i) a sizable investment in transportation; (ii) investment and technical assistance (TA) to encourage public-private partnerships (PPPs); and (iii) TA to support planning for economic corridors and sectorial policies in the transportation sector. For the ADB's efforts in these regions, DFID will provide grant co-financing of up to GBP 262 million. The 5-year initiative has been administered by ADB from March 2015 to March 2020 and did all for the growth of project like CPEC in Pakistan and Gwadar to make it beneficial for the country up to 2022.

Balochistan Before and After CPEC**1. Before**

Balochistan with five per cent of Pakistan's population and the largest land area of the country was the poorest and at the same time richest in its wealth of natural resources. Its coastal line stretches 750 km which makes up 70 per cent of Pakistan's coastline with Gwadar and Pasni being the two main seaports in the province. Due to lack of industry and few opportunities for

jobs and businesses, per capita income and average household incomes were very low. According to the Asian Development Bank (ADB), poverty rate was at 47 percent in Balochistan. Female education was 16 per cent as compared to 32 per cent in rest of the provinces in Pakistan. The population of Balochistan is around 13 million with a population density of only 19 per square kilometer compared to the national average of 166. In comparison to the national average of 166, Balochistan has a population of almost 13 million people but only 19 people per square kilometre.

2. After

Construction of roads and Gwadar are the two major projects that CPEC has started. Under the direction of CPEC, two significant road linkages are being built. The Balochistan portion of the CPEC's western route, from Kashghar to Gwadar, travels through Zhob, Quetta, Kalat, Panjgur, and Turbat before entering Gwadar through Dera Ismail Khan. This gave thousands of people job opportunity specifically, civil, electrical and architecture engineers around the province. Moreover, with the investment on CPEC it included schools making, which gave the opportunity to people study in different fields. After phase 1 and phase 2 the literacy rate of the country 30 percent and the poverty rate decreased from 47 to 25 percent.

Future Prospects of Gwadar

"To facilitate and encourage transit commerce of Central Asian Republics by offering dedicated, efficient, and cost-effective port facilities" is one of the main goals of developing Gwadar Port. The idea that transit trade from Afghanistan and the CARs will be in huge volumes is what is said to be pushing Gwadar's development as a deep sea port. With this viewpoint, the building of the Gwadar port has been justified and ought to be continued.

a. Currently, some of the transit commerce for CARs is handled in UAE ports before being transshipped to Bunder Abbas and then transported to CARs through land or rail. Double handling is required at Iranian and UAE ports. A Hub Port in Gwadar will provide direct land transportation to and from CARs.

b. Afghanistan's transit marine traffic is now handled through Karachi Port, but when the land link is constructed, it would be shifted to Gwadar.

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